

Perception of Agile Teams About Home Office During the Covid-19 Pandemic

Edna Dias Canedo^{1*}, Angelica Toffano Seidel Calazans², Isabel Sofia Brito³, Rodrigo Pereira de Mesquita¹, Pedro Henrique Teixeira Costa¹ and Eloisa Toffano Seidel Masson²

¹Department of Computer Science, University of Brasília (UnB), Brasília, DF, Brazil.

², University center – UniCEUB, Brasília, DF, Brazil.

³Computer Science, Polytechnic Institute of Beja, Bejas, Portugal.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): ednacanedo@unb.br, edna.canedo@gmail.com;
Contributing authors: angelica.toffano@gmail.com; isabel.sofia@ipbeja.pt;
rpmrodrigo@gmail.com; phtcosta@gmail.com; eloisa.masson@ceub.edu.br;

Abstract

Due to the Covid-19 pandemic there was a massive migration from the work on the office to working from home (WFH) and the software development teams had to adapt to the new reality. This paper focused on how the agile teams dealt with the challenges of WFH and how this affected the software development process. To capture the perceptions of the agile teams, we performed a survey that investigated the following: work routine, collaboration, communication, productivity, transparency, challenges and the software development process itself. Furthermore, we identified the tools and methods adopted for WFH. Our findings revealed that 1) most of the members of agile teams considered the work continued as usual regardless the place (office or remote); 2) 80% of members of agile teams informed a increase of productivity with WFH; 3) plus 85% participants are using Scrum as management strategy; 4) communication between teams members during the remote working model was perceived as more effective; and 5) Microsoft Teams and Google Meets were the interactions tools most used by members of agile teams.

Keywords: Working From Home, Agile Software Development, Communication, Productivity, Interaction.

1 RQ.1. What is the perception of agile teams related to productivity, interaction, collaboration, and communication during working from home scenario?

Aspects related to displacement:

“Use the time spent on transportation to improve the understanding of activities, to work in a noise-free environment with less interruptions”.

“The traffic and the poor quality of public transportation impose such a great strain that only this fact has already given a great advantage to remote work”.

“I can work quietly and with less pressure, delivering more. I can also work late when necessary, with no consequences or concerns of transportation”.

“Being at home, comfortable and establishing one’s own routine were differentiated factors to achieve better productivity”.

“The lack of concerns, stress and loss of time with traffic contributed a lot to the well-being, and also to perform work activities outside the conventional schedule (8am to 6pm).”

“Now I arrive at work in the state 100% productive, before I had to slow down because of the shift to work and heavy traffic, which greatly increased the level of stress.”

“The time needed for commuting to work could be used as advantage of in other ways by working remotely.”

Aspects related to well-being and productivity:

“WFH allows more focus, avoids distractions and increases availability for the company. Higher quality of life. Work with less stress and greater productivity.”

“At first, negatively, by the need for adaptation. But once adapted to the remote model, the time available for the work was longer and the breaks made during the activities were of better quality, thus allowing greater productivity”.

“Greater focus on work, fewer distraction problems. Use of remote communication tools. I believe that has greatly improved my contributions in software development, because at home we are more comfortable and our team works very well, is very committed, so the activities are performed perfectly!”

“The remote working model allowed me to work in an environment that I feel more comfortable, allied to this model I also had my work schedule relaxed. These two points created an environment where I could start working and take my breaks, which left me very motivated”.

Aspects related to information sharing and the use of tools:

“At first it was a difficult process of adaptation. With the help of tools like Microsoft Teams, Slack, Bitbucket and Jira, we could maintain good productivity.”

“The communication between the various areas of the organization has improved a lot, now it’s easy to set up a meeting room with multiple teams sharing and solving the problem in real time. Before, I had to set up a meeting or make a phone call, explain the problem. Often it was necessary to go to the other team’s room to try to solve some problem. The use of video calling tools brought teams closer together. Now we can focus on activities and suffer fewer interruptions during work, which leaves us more focused on activities.”

Some aspects mentioned that negatively affected the productivity of Agile Teams were:

Aspect related to higher individual collection:

“Lower queue control than previously happened in face-to-face, we now have more demand and more individual collection of plaintiffs who fail to realize that you are already busy.”

Aspect related to work after hours:

“Displacement time was better spent with professional activities. However, demands and activities were also carried out during lunch hours and outside of working hours, as we lost track of time and worked much more hours.”

Aspects related to household tasks:

“Conciliating domestic chores and caring for children have greatly affected my productivity.”

“I needed to reinvent myself, and to live with my concentration problems that I didn’t have or noticed at work. I learned to organize my hours and to separate hours of domestic work and hours of domestic work.”

2 RQ.2. What are the tools used by agile teams during working from home?

Table 1 presents the 4 categories and their respective subcategories. In addition, the main reasons mentioned by the participants that improved the interaction between the ICT area and the business area of the organization are presented in the Table 1. Table 2 presents the tools most used by participants to carry out the interaction between ICT and the business area; and to carry out the activities with transparency. Microsoft Teams was the tool most used by age teams to perform interactions between the ICT and business areas (mentioned by 43 participants) and to perform the activities with transparency (mentioned by 16 participants).

Table 1: Improvements Subcategories

Category	Subcategory	Detailing	# Cited
Information Sharing	Communication	Communication has become easier and more direct with the use of fast communication tools and with the exchange of instant messages by staff.	12
	Transparency	As teams are always in contact, in addition to the worksheet of activities to be carried out in WFH, we have achieved a good transparency index.	5
Continued on next page			

Table 1 – continued from previous page

Category	Subcategory	Detailing	# Cited
	Interaction	Increase in the volume of interactions between ICT and business areas.	8
		Meetings between team members have become more frequent.	11
Behavioral Change	Communication	We learn to communicate faster.	4
		Discussions do not depend on the availability of physical rooms and virtual meetings are punctual and better coordinated.	6
		Holding quick meetings to validate tasks made work more agile and helped integrate IT and business.	4
		The interactions performed virtually became more dynamic and fast.	5
		With remote work, communication had to be effective and clear.	4
		Communication has become more frequent and intense, as team members are distributed in different cities.	3
	Transparency	Product Owner (PO) needed to further clarify the acceptance criteria and test scenarios for user stories.	4
		PO started communicating daily with Agile team.	5
		The rules of business or knowledge acquired had to be more detailed and transparent, to facilitate the development of products.	3
		In WFH everything has to be well described, explained, and clarified. All information must be shared with all team members.	1
		We reinforce backlog registration in digital boards. Providing full team access to backlog, facilitating discussion in meetings	2
		We implemented a routine of meetings and reports on activities due to demands. Before there was no control of demands.	2
	Interaction	The IT and business area have learned to work together.	4
		There was already a need and trend for greater rapprochement and partnership between IT and business. This was accelerated due to the ease of communication, especially in the conduct of meetings. There are face-to-face aspects that are impaired, such as body language reading and facial expressions, but overall interactions have improved	1

Continued on next page

Table 1 – continued from previous page

Category	Subcategory	Detailing	# Cited
		Interactions between members of the age teams increased.	3
	Collaboration	The business manager, Product Owner and stakeholders became more available and accessible to ask questions and plan the next sprints.	5
		For the remote work to work well, the processes were better understood by the team and this ended up facilitating the collaboration between the team members.	3
		All members started to collaborate with the team and among themselves.	6
		There was a maturation in collective work with the perception of the need for integration of the works that were developed by the teams.	6
Tools	Communication	Easy scheduling of meetings.	17
		Screen sharing with all meeting participants facilitated the lifting of business rules and documentation, since meetings can be recorded and assisted by all participants afterwards.	5
		The recorded and made available meetings within the project folders made the flow more formal, focused and professional.	3
		Email communication improved access to stakeholders (this did not exclude formal email confirmations or other means).	5
		The time to articulate the actions of analysis, clarifications, execution of the solution and availability became smaller, considering the technological facilities that the online tools allow to accelerate more and more the service.	4
		The need for all activities to be recorded by computer tools, prevented the loss of information.	8
		Questions are resolved more quickly. Just put the question on Slack and mark the responsible person who in a few minutes the person responds.	6
	Transparency	The need to manage people and processes remotely made the company investing in monitoring tools. Thus allowing greater control over what is being developed and by whom.	7

Continued on next page

Table 1 – continued from previous page

Category	Subcategory	Detailing	# Cited
		Greater records of activities to prove remote work, such as recording, shared archiving, or sending to groups.	3
	Interaction	The use of Scrum, Kanban and Design Thinking has also contributed to better interaction among team members, especially the Product Owners with the team.	4
		Members of Agile Teams quickly adapted to remote living and made very good use of the available technological resources, with very few exceptions.	3
	Collaboration	At WFH it's easier to ask for help. Sharing screens in meetings allows for collaborative help among all meeting participants.	5
Productivity		A more rigid digital control was implemented, which enabled a more efficient monitoring of productivity.	3
		More concentration at work, not distracted by side conversations.	9
		I feel more productive by the freedom I have to manage my own time.	23

3 RQ.3. What are the challenges faced by agile teams during working from home and how were they solved or mitigated?

Some challenges mentioned by Agile Teams were:

“The biggest challenges were the high turnover of the software factory team. Not by the remote model itself, but by the current ICT labor market scenario, especially in the development area.”

“WFH’s challenges are different, not all people open the cameras, and we lose visual contact, perception of body language, the company has not bought other tools that help in the sharing of ideas in a playful way. Some teams had employees without access to corporate Teams, not being able to be in the same chat and so we lost this feeling of being sitting next to each other.”

“The main difficulty was dealing with members who did not show the minimum of discipline with remote work.”

“The main difficulties are dealing with professionals who use the freedom of the home office for procrastination and/or solving particular problems (go out to shop, go to the gym, travel, etc, even at office hours). There was also a problem in dealing with professionals who were very focused on work and did not look at messaging services, becoming inaccessible for several hours a day.”

“I believe it was more challenging due to the difficulties in maintaining efficient communication. Although productivity has improved, communication has worsened, as people are no closer. Each remains focused on their work without interacting with other team members.”

Table 2 Tools used by Agile Teams

Activity	Tools	# Cited
Interaction between ICT and Business	Kanban	3
	Trello	7
	IdeaBoardz	1
	Google Meets	14
	Microsoft Teams	43
	WhatsApp	3
	Jira	5
	Swagger	1
	Zoom	2
	Slack	3
	Discord	2
	Redmine	2
	E-mail	3
Transparency	IdeaBoardz	1
	Trello	8
	WhatsApp	3
	Jira	5
	Kanban	4
	Swagger	1
	Git	2
	Microsoft Teams	16
	Skype	1
	Discord	3
	Google Meets	6
	Zoom	1
	Slack	2
Redmine	2	

“Remotely it was more challenging with agile teams, because communication is essential, and we had a lot of difficulty in communication between teams and transparency of activities and projects between squads.”

We quote below some of the solutions mentioned by Agile Teams were:

“ More frequent meetings and conversations, in addition to periodic reports and strict application of minimum service levels control indexes.”

“Offer practitioners frequent training, coaching, creation of backlog evolution indicators, training and mentoring with the team.”

“Carry out a closer follow-up with all team members, stimulating communication and debates between team members.”

Survey participants mentioned other important considerations that were not addressed in Survey:

“Regarding the health of members of the agile teams, there were fewer departures during the pandemic.”

“Issues such as the costs of working from home and the cost of expenses, even partial, still need to be better addressed by companies. Also, the evaluation of results, performance and dedication of team members.”

“The diversity of profiles and some aspects of remote work require attention, especially aspects related to mental health.”

“The lack of empathy in understanding that people who are on the other side due to the pandemic may be experiencing motivation, family or health problems, is a factor that needs to be discussed and mentioned by individuals. Understanding that remote work is not Home Office is an important point. Bringing light to these and other issues have brought gain to our Agile team.”

“The turnover in the ICT area was very high with the advent of the pandemic, which greatly hampered the work of agile teams that needed to devote more hours to meet their demands.”

4 Questions of Survey

1. Please tell us your Country, State and City where that you work. *

2. How old are you? *

- less than 21 years
- 21 to 25 years
- 26 to 30 years
- 31 to 35 years
- 36 to 40 years
- 41 to 45 years
- 46 to 50 years
- 51 to 55 years old
- 56 to 60 years
- over 60 years

3. What is your education level? *

- Graduation student
- Graduation
- Specialization
- Master’s degree
- Doctorate degree
- Post doctoral

4. How long have you been working in the ITC (Information Technology and Communication) field? *

- less than 1 year
- from 1 to 3 years old
- From 4 to 6 years
- from 7 to 10 years
- from 11 to 15 years old

from 16 to 20 years old
more than 20 years

5. What is the area of activity of the organization in which you participate/participated in a software development project? *

Federal Public Administration
State Public Administration
State company (Serpro, BB, CEF, Correios, etc.)
Private software development company
Collaboration/research projects
Open-source projects

6. What was the main role (functions) that you play/have played in a software development project? *

Requirements analyst
Software engineer
Specialist in human computer interaction
Project manager
Data modeling
Software programmer/developer
Designer / Designer
Software tester
I have never participated in a software development project

Pandemic related issues

7. When did your institution suspend face-to-face personal activities due to Covid-19? Please reply using DD/MM/YYYY. If not suspended, reply "Not suspended". *
8. Check the alternatives that define your professional life after the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. *

My workplace was closed, and I could not carry out activities remotely.
My workplace was closed, but activities continued fully, in remote mode.
My workplace was closed, but activities continued partially, in remote mode.
My workplace was not closed, but activities continued partially, in remote mode.
My workplace was not closed, and activities continued face-to-face.
My workplace was partially closed, and activities continued

9. In your opinion, has this period of closure of organizations that imposed an adaptation to remote work affected your productivity? *

No
Yes - negatively
Yes - positively

10. Why?

Questions related to agile teams

11. What agile method / framework do you use? *

10 *Perception of Agile Teams About Home Office During the Covid-19 Pandemic*

Kanban
Scrumban
XP
scrum
Other

12. What is your current role on the team? *

Coach
Developer
Scrum Master
Product Owner
Other

13. Has the interaction between IT and the business area improved with the adoption of remote work? *

I totally disagree
I disagree
Neutral
I agree
I totally agree

14. Why?

15. What tools and methods were adopted?

16. Has transparency (understanding what needs to be done, what is being done, etc.) improved with the adoption of remote work? *

I totally disagree
I disagree
Neutral
I agree
I totally agree

17. Why?

18. What tools and methods were adopted?

19. Has collaboration between development team members improved with the adoption of remote work?
*

I totally disagree
I disagree
Neutral
I agree
I totally agree

20. Why?

21. What tools and methods were adopted?
22. Has team communication become more effective with the adoption of remote work? *
 - I totally disagree
 - I disagree
 - Neutral
 - I agree
 - I totally agree
23. Why?
24. What tools and methods were adopted?
25. Has your agile team become more productive with the adoption of remote work? *
 - I totally disagree
 - I disagree
 - Neutral
 - I agree
 - I totally agree
26. Why?
27. What tools and methods were adopted?
28. Were impediments or problems resolved more quickly with the adoption of remote work? *
 - I totally disagree
 - I disagree
 - Neutral
 - I agree
 - I totally agree
29. Why?
30. What tools and methods were adopted?
31. Could you describe whether, in your perception, working with agile teams remotely was more challenging than in person. Did you encounter the same difficulties and challenges? Or did others appear? Which are?
32. What were the solutions and proposals to mitigate or improve this remote work process?
33. Could you describe other considerations that you think are important that were not addressed in the questionnaire.